

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	11	B		Min: 67584 Max: (one point)	1339 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No
 In elevation drawing? Yes No
 Photos: Yes No #: 153-46
 Photo Model: Yes No #: 207

DEFINITION
 RUBBLE INCLUDING SKULL
 Covered by SU:
 Fills 156-158
 Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles M <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dolia R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mortar M <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris F <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails R (1) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marble R <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) F <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clay 40% <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Silt 60% <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)

SOIL/MATRIX
 clay 40% silt 60% sand 0%
 Granular Layered Cohesive

Compaction	Color
<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit (LIMIT OF GEOTEXTILE)
 Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit } unclear

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: _____ Is bound to (only for masonry): _____
 Is abutted by: _____ Abuts: _____
 Is covered by: 0.5 _____ Covers: _____
 Is cut by: _____ Cuts: _____
 Is filled by: _____ Fills: 1363

OBSERVATIONS
 layer of rubble, including mortar, limestone and a human skull, below the skull a fragment of a lime sarcophagus lid was found

△
292

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: Southeastern corner @ 2011 Excavation Limit (at limit of Geotextile)
 Shape: Rough oval shape

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): downwards slope at Southern limit; skull, tile fragments (sparse)
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): walking/paving Marble slab (possibly from/similar to 1325)
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): decreases toward south
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
 Observations:

e.g. "Seitgepäß"

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

~~Disturbed graves~~
 Disturbed graves due to disarticulated body → found cranium, vertebrae fragments and one phalange. Skull is most likely incomplete. Fill in SU seems to be collapsed. debris.

Disturbed by ploughing or heding

Skull fragments to be lifted by Supervisors

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by SLOSH, DRO, AB

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on